

Appendix D: Qualitative Codebook

Codes derived from thematic analysis of 30 vendor interviews organized by research question. Each code includes definition and representative quote from interview data.

RQ1: Vendor Perceptions and Attitudes

PERCEPTION-LIFECYCLE-CONTROL.

OTA framed as post-shipment product control mechanism rather than security infrastructure. Vendors view OTA primarily as capability to modify deployed devices when physical access no longer practical, with security treated as one application rather than primary motivation.

Example: “For IoT products, OTA is the product’s second life. After devices are shipped, fixes, optimizations, and feature additions all rely on OTA.” [V21]

PERCEPTION-REACTIVE-SECURITY.

Security understanding of OTA emerges from experience rather than anticipation. Vendors shift attitude toward security after concrete incidents causing direct loss (recalls, compensation, disclosed vulnerabilities) rather than proactive threat modeling.

Example: “There was a hardcoded password vulnerability in a smart camera product. More than 100,000 devices had to be recalled, and the direct loss exceeded 2.5 million USD. Only after that did we truly realize the role of OTA in product security.” [V12]

PERCEPTION-COMPLIANCE-HEDGE.

Regulatory requirements perceived as moving targets that evolve over time and vary across markets. OTA viewed as defensive capability to preserve market eligibility under evolving regulations, allowing post-shipment adaptation when compliance expectations shift.

Example: “For overseas markets, requirements are not static. Even if you pass certification today, the rules may change next year. OTA is the only way to make sure products already in the field can still comply.” [V7]

RQ2: OTA Practices and Resource Allocation

PRACTICE-WHITE-LABEL-SHARING.

Multiple branded products share same firmware core, OTA backend, and cryptographic credentials. Differences between brands limited to configuration or UI elements while signing keys and update logic remain identical across brand boundaries.

Example: “We do not have a professional key management team. Managing separate keys would increase the risk of mistakes or loss. Different brands use the same core firmware; the differences are mostly logo, UI, or configuration. The signing and update mechanism is shared.” [V11]

PRACTICE-CROSS-BRAND-PROPAGATION.

Vulnerabilities discovered in one brand affect other brands using identical firmware, with detection occurring asynchronously through brand-specific user complaints rather than infrastructure indicating shared exposure.

Example: “One brand reported a problem first. Later we found other brands using the same firmware had the same issue, just not reported yet. We do not have a list of all brands affected by a specific internal module; when something happens, we investigate step by step.” [V6]

PRACTICE-CLOUD-PLATFORM-CONSTRAINTS.

Cloud platforms limit OTA safety mechanisms and change APIs unilaterally. Vendors wanted device-state-aware triggers (updating when charging/idle) but cloud interfaces support only immediate or scheduled updates, forcing abandonment of safety mechanisms.

Example: Vendors report cloud platforms can change APIs without notice, disrupting OTA delivery until advance notification agreements negotiated.

PRACTICE-UPDATE-FREQUENCY-DIVERGENCE.

Self-brand vendors concentrate at quarterly intervals (32.9%, survey data) with 58.3% updating monthly or more (survey data). OEM vendors cluster at reactive end: 33.3% update only when issues arise, 16.7% rarely update (survey data). 50% reactive majority among OEM vendors vs 29.2% self-brand (survey data).

Example: Half of respondents require 1–4 weeks to

prepare typical update, other half require 1–3 months (survey data). 40% report 20–60 person-days per update (survey data).

PRACTICE-VALIDATION-BURDEN.

Dominant OTA workload is validation against failure modes appearing only under real deployment conditions. Testing disconnection, power loss, insufficient memory, extreme conditions takes more time than development itself.

Example: “The most time-consuming part is testing. We must simulate disconnection, power loss, insufficient memory, and other extreme conditions to check whether the device bricks. This takes more time than development itself.” [V28]

RESOURCE-ALLOCATION-PATTERNS.

Medium companies allocate only 10% to OTA (44% reduction from small companies’ 18%) (survey data). Large companies 15% (survey data). Medium companies’ minimal OTA allocation coincides with maximal hardware investment (38%) (survey data). Large companies face compliance costs 5x higher (25% vs 5%) yet allocate 50% more to OTA than medium (survey data).

RESOURCE-CEILING-CONSTRAINT.

Small firms appear only above 23,000 units and never exceed 2.3 updates annually regardless of sales volume (Phase 1 measurement data). Large firms operate across entire sales spectrum and reach 8.82 updates/year (Phase 1 measurement data).

RQ3: Supply Chain Responsibility

SUPPLY-CHAIN-FRAGMENTATION. OTA stack spans chip vendors, SDK providers, cloud platforms, device manufacturers with no single entity possessing complete visibility. Typical distribution involves 5+ parties: chip vendors (flash/drivers), module vendors (network), manufacturers (firmware), cloud platforms (distribution), customers (deployment) (interview data).

Example: “Once upgrade failure rate was abnormally high. Chip vendor said it was our app logic problem. App team said chip driver was unstable. Final resolution: whoever’s territory, their responsibility. When truly unclear, we all meet together, pull logs line by line until we find the culprit.” [V10]

SUPPLY-CHAIN-REACTIVE-COORDINATION. When OTA updates fail, fragmented structure creates immediate responsibility ambiguity. Vendors universally report pattern of mutual blame, joint forensic investigation, negotiated attribution based on log analysis. Three-day investigation windows before identifying root causes in upstream components (interview

data). No pre-established security incident response procedures.

SUPPLY-CHAIN-CHIP-DEPENDENCY.

Chip vendors occupy most privileged position controlling bootloader integrity, secure boot, flash partitioning, driver availability. Chip support life-cycles (2–5 years) shorter than device deployment (5–10 years) (interview data). When chip support terminates: 0.4M USD cost, 20-person team, 3 months for reverse-engineering to maintain 500K devices (interview data).

Example: “When chip vendor provided driver support, patch cost was approximately 6,000 USD. After chip vendor stopped support, our self-development cost exceeded 200,000 USD.” [V26]

SUPPLY-CHAIN-SDK-OPACITY.

SDK providers supply pre-packaged modules as compiled libraries without source access, creating information asymmetry where security properties cannot be independently verified. Opacity delays vulnerability detection: manufacturers initially misattribute symptoms to own code. 3-day diagnostic windows before correctly identifying upstream SDK defects (interview data).

SUPPLY-CHAIN-UPSTREAM-

RESPONSE-DELAY. Industrial IoT products face median response times 14–45 days vs 5–14 days consumer IoT (survey data). Over 75% requests exceed 7-day threshold for critical security patches (survey data). Large vendors experience longest delays despite stronger supplier relationships (survey data).

SUPPLY-CHAIN-COST-TRANSFER.

Economic structure creates systematic cost transfer to device manufacturers. Upstream partners capture revenue at service initiation while imposing ongoing costs through discontinuation, interface changes, pricing adjustments that materialize years later and cannot be recovered through pricing adjustments for already-sold devices.

RQ4: Economic Factors and Lifecycle

ECON-DEVELOPMENT-FIXED-COST. Development costs (35–40% expenditure, survey data) exhibit fixed-cost economics: developing unified OTA backend with secure signing requires 3–4 engineers investing many months (interview data), regardless of whether 10K or 1M units ship.

ECON-CLOUD-LINEAR-SCALING. Cloud infrastructure costs (20–25%, survey data) scale linearly with device population. Per-device pricing (0.02 USD per push, interview data). 1M devices incurs 130K USD annually in platform fees (interview data).

ECON-TESTING-COMBINATORIAL.

Testing costs (15%, survey data) grow combinatorially with firmware versions, device variants, and deployment environments. Test equipment alone 20K USD for 20 device models (interview data).

ECON-COMPLIANCE-PER-UNIT-DIFFERENTIAL. Compliance costs (10–15%, survey data) create per-unit differentials: 6K USD penetration test costs 0.05 USD/device at 1M units vs 0.7 USD at 10K units (interview data).

ECON-OPERATIONS-HIDDEN-COSTS. Operations and maintenance (10–15%, survey data) lack visibility during initial planning. Single upgrade failure requiring nationwide engineer dispatch: 11.5K USD travel costs alone (interview data).

ECON-VERSION-FRAGMENTATION. Version fragmentation: maintaining V1.0 through V3.5 simultaneously results in code repositories exceeding 2TB (interview data). 10 versions require testing dozens of upgrade paths (interview data).

ECON-SUPPORT-DURATION-FORMULA. Vendors treat support duration as calculated output from economic inputs. Explicit viability formulas: support years = (sale price - hardware cost) / annual OTA cost (interview data).

Example: “Our formula: support years equals sale price minus hardware cost, divided by annual OTA cost. High-end smart meters at 428 USD get 10-year updates. Low-end sensors at 14 USD, after two years we recommend buying new ones.” [V2]

ECON-MARGIN-CONSUMPTION. For low-margin product (unit price 8.5 USD, 20% gross margin), 5-year OTA costs consume approximately 68% of total profit (interview data). Smart plugs at 12.7 USD with 30% margin require 50K unit shipments to cover OTA costs (interview data).

ECON-TIERED-SUPPORT-POLICY. Economic formulas translate into tiered policies: flagship products above 285 USD receive 3–5 years support for brand image (interview data). Entry-level products under 15 USD ship as-is with perhaps one free upgrade, subsequent updates rely on users buying new devices (interview data).

ECON-REGULATORY-COLLISION. EU Cyber Resilience Act mandates 5-year support floor, colliding with vendor economics. 5-year OTA costs already exceed product profit by 3x or more (interview data). Vendors describe three responses: market exit, price increases, or category abandonment (interview data).

Example: “Current pricing cannot cover five years for low-profit products. If regulations force five-year updates, we will most likely abandon the low-end market.” [V4]

RQ5: Technical and Structural Constraints

CONSTRAINT-HARDWARE-THRESHOLD. Memory and storage as hard boundaries below which security mechanisms become technically impossible. Devices with only few KB memory cannot run encryption or store dual-bank systems for rollback, making secure OTA infeasible.

Example: “Five-year-old streetlight controllers have only 4MB flash. Cannot run basic encryption. We ultimately abandoned security verification entirely.” [V19]

CONSTRAINT-FLASH-ENDURANCE. Flash write cycle limitations create tension between testing thoroughness and hardware longevity. Frequent OTA testing during development accelerates chip wear, forcing vendors to minimize write operations and reduce comprehensiveness of failure-mode validation before deployment.

CONSTRAINT-TOOLCHAIN-EXPIRATION. Toolchain collapse emerges gradually as upstream dependencies lose support, creating devices that become technically unpatchable regardless of vendor resources or regulatory obligations.

Example: “Our 2020 smart band needed a security patch last year. Development tools would not install on new computers. Library files had no download source. Finally found old laptop preserving the original environment. Barely completed patch development.” [V30]

CONSTRAINT-INSTITUTIONAL-KNOWLEDGE. Patching 5-year-old products requires bringing back original engineers or spending substantial resources reverse-engineering old code. Patches costing 7,150 USD with vendor support can exceed 29,000 USD after support ends (4x increase) (interview data).

CONSTRAINT-SDK-LIFECYCLE-MISMATCH. Structural mismatch: chip vendor SDK support typically lasts 2–5 years while IoT products remain deployed 5–10 years (interview data). Devices become technically unpatchable regardless of vendor intent or regulatory mandate.

CONSTRAINT-DEPLOYMENT-ENVIRONMENT. Devices deployed globally encounter environmental extremes causing components to behave differently than in testing. Weak WiFi causes 99% complete downloads to fail (interview data). African deployments require battery-threshold policies (interview data). Mining installations achieve only 60% success rates

(interview data).

Example: “At minus 30 degrees in Northeast China, device CRC verification kept failing. Finally discovered flash read-write anomaly at low temperature.” [V23]

CONSTRAINT-INFRASTRUCTURE-FRAGMENTATION. Network and power infrastructure compound challenges. Carriers intercept specific long connections causing devices to miss upgrade instructions, requiring continuous optimization of heartbeat strategies (interview data). Regional app stores impose distinct requirements: Huawei, Xiaomi, OPPO each impose distinct review rules (interview data).

CONSTRAINT-DATA-PLAN-LIMITS. Some carriers limit monthly data to 100MB, forcing large updates transmitted across three months and extending vulnerability windows (interview data). Cloud platforms also limit safety mechanisms: vendors cannot implement device-state-aware triggers (interview data).